

ACP96 results for 2020

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Summary ACP96 operation

- Data acquisition done with custom matlab software
- Measurements available on 54 nights
- Analysis by Reda:
 - Calibration periods analysed separately.
 - Measurement data submitted only for signal levels $U \leq -800 \mu\text{V}$.

ACP96 calibration

- Calibrations are based on the method proposed by Reda by regularly cooling the ACP with a bottom plate and using the resulting measurements to retrieve the responsivity.

The selection of points for the fit has a significant influence on the retrieved responsivity:

$$C_{\text{Reda}} = 13.00 \mu\text{V}/(\text{Wm}^{-2})$$

$$C^1_{\text{PMOD}} = 12.18 \mu\text{V}/(\text{Wm}^{-2})$$

$$C^2_{\text{PMOD}} = 12.72 \mu\text{V}/(\text{Wm}^{-2})$$

For this particular calibration process, the responsivities retrieved by Reda and PMOD¹ or PMOD² differ by 6.7 % and 2.2% respectively, with Reda giving the higher responsivity.

PMOD selection procedure:

- 1) choose initial datapoint set for cooling period
 - 1) PMOD¹ : dT range = 10 minutes
 - 2) PMOD² : dT range = 8 minutes
- 2) Make linear fit, *res* are the residuals of this fit.
- 3) Remove all points from dataset that are more than $2 \cdot \text{std}(\text{res})$.
- 4) repeat linear fit with the new selection of datapoints
- 5) Slope represents the retrieved responsivity of the ACP.

The procedure implemented at PMOD/WRC is automated and uses objective criteria (C^1_{PMOD} is the selected version).

ACP96 calibrations for 2020

The mean difference between C_{REDA} and C^1_{PMOD} is 5%, with a variability of 2.5%.

(With C^2_{PMOD} the mean difference is $0.3 \pm 2\%$)

ACP96 longwave irradiance measurements

Calibration event produces irradiance changes of $\sim 3 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$, indicating that the instrument is not in steady-state. (Which is the case for the measurements between calibrations where the calibration results are applied).

ACP96 longwave irradiance measurements

ACP96 operation at PMOD

- The data acquisition program is based on custom software developed by PMOD.
- The analysis of the calibration events are very sensitive to the selection of points during the cooling event.
- The calibration analysis by PMOD and REDA can be made to agree by choosing specific criteria (PMOD²).
- The other choice of criteria produces the irradiance dataset PMOD¹ which is several Wm⁻² smaller than REDA or PMOD².
- The irradiance retrieved during the calibration periods shows variations to the steady-state conditions of ~3 Wm⁻², indicating that during the calibration period the instrument is not in the steady-state as during the measurements afterwards. This is probably due to temperature gradients inside of the instrument because the cooling is from the bottom.
- Using the FORGAN equation with conduction term and calibration based on 2019 comparison to IRIS2 (see PMOD/WRC Annual Report 2019, page 13).

$$E = \frac{U}{C} + k_1 \sigma T_r^4 + k_2 \sigma T_c^4 + k_3 (T_r - T_c) \quad \text{with } C=10.12 \mu\text{V}/(\text{Wm}^{-2}), k_1=0.98, k_2=0.0285, k_3=8.07$$

Comparison ACP96 with IRIS and WISG

Comparison ACP96 with IRIS and WISG

Comparison ACP96 with IRIS and WISG

ACP_{REDA}

ACP_{PMOD1}

ACP_{FORGAN}

IRIS2

WISG

Comparison ACP96 with IRIS and WISG

ACP_{REDA}

ACP_{PMOD1}

ACP_{FORGAN}

IRIS2

WISG

Comparison ACP96 with IRIS and WISG

24-25 November 2020

ACP IRIS at PMOD/WRC

ACP_{REDA}

ACP_{PMOD1}

ACP_{FORGAN}

IRIS2

WISG

Comparison ACP96 with IRIS and WISG

The ACP using the outdoor calibration procedure (ACP_{PMOD1} and ACP_{REDA}) has a significant dependence with IWP relative to IRIS, which is not the case for ACP_{FORGAN}.

Differences to IRIS2 all conditions

Instrument	Difference to IRIS2 / (Wm ⁻²)	Nb. Measurements
ACP96 _{PMOD1}	3.6±3.0	25168
ACP96 _{REDA}	7.0±2.8	4020
ACP96 _{FORGAN}	2.7±1.4	25486
IRIS2	0.4±1.1	25200
WISG	-2.9±1.5	27425

Differences to IRIS2 IWV > 10 mm

Instrument	Difference to IRIS2 / (Wm ⁻²)	Nb. Measurements
ACP96 _{PMOD1}	-0.4 ± 1.6	4273
ACP96 _{REDA}	3.9 ± 0.8	202
ACP96 _{FORGAN}	2.1 ± 0.6	4273
IRIS2	-1.0 ± 0.9	5388
WISG	-4.6 ± 0.9	5388

Conclusions

- 1) The ACP96 was operated during 54 nights on mostly clear sky conditions
- 2) The calibrations of ACP96 are based on "cooling events" performed every 3 hours.
- 3) The calibration factors retrieved from these calibrations are very sensitive to the selection of the measurement points used for the analysis (retrieval of linear slope).
- 4) The calibration factor of ACP96 retrieved during a calibration period produces inconsistent results when applied to this period. This indicates that the ACP96 is not in steady-state during the calibration, most probably due to temperature gradients within the instrument, which is also confirmed with the ACP_{FORGAN} dataset.
- 5) The ACP96 shows a significant dependence with IWV, when compared to IRIS2&IRIS4. This is also much higher than what is observed with respect to the WISG.
- 6) Using a constant responsivity for the whole period of 2020 does not improve the observed seasonal dependence on IWV using ACP_{PMOD1avg} .
- 7) The ACP96 with the $PMOD^1$ calibration agrees very well with IRIS2&IRIS4 for $IWV > 10$ mm.
- 8) The FORGAN equation produces the best consistency with IRIS2&IRIS4 and very little seasonal dependence on IWV. The observed offset of 2 Wm^{-2} is an indication that the calibration performed in 2019 is not adequate anymore (possible degradation?).